

A comparison of traditional casting techniques with current 3D scanning methods

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Abstract

For decades, shoe and tire impression marks have been preserved primarily using plaster or sulfur casts. While the composition of materials used in plaster casts has evolved—particularly toward dental plasters that reproduce details with high precision—a persistent concern remains in the minds of many users: Especially at temperatures at around +4°C (39°F) and below, the long setting time supposedly extends the time spent at the crime scene. Due to time constraints, plaster casts are therefore often omitted, and the scene is merely documented photographically, which severely limits the possibilities for unambiguous attribution or reliable exclusion of a trace to a specific shoe. The article describes the testing of a dental plaster used in forensic evidence collection under various temperature conditions. In addition, alternative, non-contact methods such as 3D scanning and photogrammetry are tested and finally compared with the results of traditional plaster casts to determine whether current digital 3D scanning methods are suitable as reliable comparison methods.

KEYWORDS

dental plaster; shoe impression; footprint, shoe print, casting; evidence recovery; footwear impression; photogrammetry; three-dimensional; tire impression; tyre impression; tire print; glove impression

Introduction

When evaluating shoe, tire, or glove impressions, it is extremely important that the impressions found at the crime scene be preserved using a reliable and detailed method. Taking two-dimensional photographs of these marks is an important preliminary step in evidence collection; however, in most cases, they are sufficient only for so-called “group classification”—that is, for assigning the mark to a specific shoe, tire, or glove model—and rarely for identification or an assessment level beyond the non-liquet level. In practice, assigning a trace to a specific source is only possible with photographs in exceptional cases. For this reason, more suitable methods for securing shoe or tire impression traces must be used for the purpose of identification or reliable exclusion.

Fig. 1: Creation of a shoe impression

Current methods for securing shoe impressions at crime scenes

Currently, shoe, tire, and glove impressions are typically photographed first (as a preliminary safety measure) and, depending on the quality of the impression, cast to create a permanent 3D image. Photographing impression traces is done under specific conditions, such as taking a plane-parallel, full-frame shot using a tripod and an off-camera flash or similar device to avoid flashing directly into the trace and to highlight contours through side lighting [1]. In the meantime, mobile lighting frames have already been developed in Germany and China that are placed on top of the print and illuminate it from multiple angles to achieve optimal illumination. These devices replace the off-camera flash.

Another key criterion for forensically acceptable 2D trace photography is the placement of the scale on the trace base, i.e., the depth level at which the identifying features intended for analysis are located. The L-scale must therefore be dug into the ground next to the trace in a way that does not damage it. If the scale is not placed at the correct depth, this will inevitably lead to measurement deviations during forensic analysis by an expert in shoe, tire, and glove traces (in this example, by as much as 2 cm). Of course, the camera must be positioned close enough to the shoe impression so that the trace fills the entire display.

Fig. 2: Creating a photo of a shoe impression

As mentioned above; to make the contours of a trace visible, it is often necessary to create a shadow (using sidelight, such as side flashes, light panels, or light frames). Several methods can be helpful in increasing the contrast of a trace, especially in snow. Some forensic techniques use a carbon black powder mixture, others sprinkle wax powder into the track, and others use commercially available wax spray to make the track contours more visible for photography.

Successful track photography is usually followed by the casting of the shoe or tire impression. While *alabaster plaster* was used as a molding agent in the past, dental plasters emerged as a more effective method in Germany starting around 1980. Today, there are also significant differences among dental plasters in terms of detail accuracy, dimensional stability, fracture sensitivity, and hardening time.

Bremen Plaster Project

In 2022, the Forensic Science Institute of the Bremen in the State Criminal Police Office conducted a preliminary study aimed at identifying a dental impression material from a range of dental plasters that would be highly suitable for field use. A wide variety of dental plasters were available for selection, and the institute contacted numerous manufacturers to inquire about their newest products. The primary criterion for selection was hardening time, provided that detail accuracy, a negligible shrinkage index, and fracture behavior remained within acceptable limits. The selection fell on the dental hard plaster *Pico-Crema Soft* from the German company *Picodent*. The plaster was blue, but the manufacturer could have mixed it with other color pigments upon request. The color scheme is very important for subsequent photography.

After the type of plaster was selected, the curing behavior - including the curing time - at various temperatures was to be tested and determined as part of the Bremen Plaster Project [6] through laboratory experiments, which were additionally complemented by random sampling of realistic impression trials. Since a variety of factors influence the setting time, an experimental setup was created that focuses on the temperature factor and eliminates the other influencing variables as much as possible. To reach this target, measurements of the plaster temperature were taken at different ambient temperatures to determine how long the plaster samples required to harden.

The test track served as the basis for the plaster impressions in the project. Therefore, it had to provide exactly the same conditions for every impression. An impression track in sand or topsoil was impractical, as there would have been too much variation, and the moisture from the substrate might have influenced the curing times. For this reason, a solid silicone test trace was chosen. This had the advantage that the cavity remained constant for each test casting, preventing any variation. Additionally, silicone is suitable for the temperature ranges involved and remains flexible even at low temperatures, which simplified demolding. To measure the temperature at the center of the mold, a hole was created in the silicone mold for a temperature sensor.

Fig. 3: Test track of the comparison sole made of silicone

The setting process of plaster is a chemical process in which the powdered plaster material is transformed into a solid, durable substance. This process is triggered by the addition of water. When mixed with water, the plaster material forms a suspension known as plaster slurry. In this process, the plaster crystals are enveloped by the water and begin to slowly dissolve. As the plaster material dissolves, the calcium and sulfate ions begin

to combine and form calcium sulfate hydrate crystals. These crystals begin to grow and eventually bond together to form a solid material. This process is called hydration or setting. The setting process of plaster is exothermic, meaning that heat is released during the process.

In the test series, the plaster casting was performed at several temperatures (-20, -10, 0, +10, +20, +30, and +40 °C). The mold was brought to the respective test temperature before filling it with plaster. The water used to mix with the plaster powder had a temperature of 20°C. Humidity and air pressure remained constant. At each temperature, a minimum of 5 casting tests were performed to determine an average temperature curve that could be compared in a diagram.

Fig. 4: Performing the experiment with dental plaster

Based on the measured temperature curves, it appears that ambient temperature has only a minor effect on the setting process of gypsum. When comparing the curves across different temperature ranges, low ambient temperatures cause the peak of the temperature curve to shift backwards by a maximum of 20 minutes.

Fig. 5: Temperature-time curve per temperature range

The experiments yielded several highly positive findings regarding the use of dental plasters. It was confirmed that modern dental hard plasters are very well suited for casting crime scene evidence due to their high level of accuracy. Furthermore, it was determined that, depending on the ambient temperature, the cast can be

removed after 30 to 45 minutes at the latest. The influence of ambient temperature on the setting process is significantly less than expected and extends the setting time until demolding is possible by only a few minutes, not by hours, as initially reported by the forensic team at the start of the experiments. Since the setting process occurs as an exothermic reaction, ambient temperature has only a minor influence on the reaction process. Even temperatures around -20°C only slightly delayed the reaction. The water temperature, on the other hand, had a noticeable influence on the working time and the start of the exothermic setting process. Thus, at high ambient temperatures, the working time can be extended by adding cold water during mixing.

Thermal imaging was used to demonstrate how the plaster heated up during the setting process. In the subsequent test, the outside temperature was approximately 22°C (Fig. 6 / 7).

Fig. 6: Thermal image of the casting after 3 minutes (left) and after 12 minutes (right), values in $^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fig. 7: Thermal image of the casting after 28 minutes (left) and after 107 minutes (right), values in $^{\circ}\text{C}$

It was found that, provided there is a sufficient amount of plaster, the strength of the plaster cast is already high enough after about 30 minutes that reinforcement is not necessary and the cast can still be removed. It therefore seems advisable to use slightly more plaster than too little in practice to ensure sufficient strength. A more stable impression is particularly important with regard to transport and subsequent handling. The amount of 900 g of plaster used in this project appears appropriate for many impression casts and results in a very stable impression that is easy to handle and has little risk of breaking during demolding or transport. The optimal amount of water added was approximately 450 ml.

Tab. 1: Setting times for Picodent Crema Soft blue dental hard plaster

Outside temperature [°C]	Outside temperature [°F]	time [min]
+ 40	+ 104	32
+ 30	+ 86	34
+ 20	+ 68	35
+ 10	+ 50	37
0	+ 32	40
- 10	+ 14	43
- 20	- 4	45

Tip: In very warm temperatures, adding a small amount of regular dish soap (e.g., Fit) or citric acid can slow down the setting of the plaster. But be careful: adding too much of these substances can negatively affect the porosity and stability of the cast! Additionally, the resulting foam can cause bubbles, which have a negative impact on the quality of the cast. If cold water is available, it can also be used to delay the setting of the plaster.

Laboratory tests were also conducted to determine when the plaster had achieved so-called *demolding strength*, allowing it to be removed from the mold without damage. Since the test mold was made of silicone, the demolding process proved to be significantly more difficult than it would be with sand or soil at a crime scene. The demolding times recorded in the laboratory differed significantly from the values in the tables (at approx. 20°C after 20 min).

Imaging accuracy

Due to their special composition, dental hard plasters offer excellent impression accuracy, allowing even the smallest details to be visible in the impression. One disadvantage, however, is that air bubbles can form when the plaster is mixed, which then collect at the edges of the impression elements and may harden there. Individual characteristics at these locations could be overlaid by the bubbles and negatively impact the evaluation.

In the laboratory, bubble formation could be prevented using shaking or vibrating plates; however, this option is not available in the practical situation at the crime scene. To counteract this, the plaster mixture should have the lowest possible viscosity so that the air bubbles have the possibility to rise within the mixture. If the plaster mixture is already relatively firm when poured into the mold, the air bubbles usually remain at the collection points and harden there. This behavior can be observed, for example, in the ready-mix products from the company *Sirchie*, "*Shake-N-Cast*" (1200 g with 414 ml of water), at temperatures of approximately 10 °C and above. For this reason, it is recommended that the plaster be mixed to a more liquid consistency (approx. 450 ml water to 900 g plaster) so that the cast can flow out smoothly. This prevents bubble formation for the most part.

The sole used to create the silicone mold had fine surface structures incorporated by the manufacturer, and additional defects were also introduced. The silicone captured the surface structures of the sole with near-perfect detail. To demonstrate the accuracy of the cast, castings were produced using plaster and Stewalin.

Fig. 8: Reference shoe sole; some of specific features of the sole have been marked

Fig. 9: Plaster cast *pico-crema soft blue* made at 20°C

Fig. 10: *Stewalin* cast made at 20°C

For comparison, here is an impression made with the dental hard plaster *pico-crema soft blue* (Fig. 9) and an impression made using the model casting material *Stewalin* (Fig. 10).

In both impressions, the obvious features and damage (see red arrows for examples) of the reference sole are reproduced in great detail. Surprisingly, even many of the letters, as well as the shoe size indication in the joint area (outlined in red), are clearly legible. These details will be discussed in more detail later when comparing them with 3D scanning methods.

Digital 3D recording methods

For decades, the casting of impression tracks using plaster, sulfur, and other liquid casting materials has proven to be an effective method for preserving impression tracks at crime scenes in three dimensions. However, the question arises as to how this type of preservation might be outdated and if modern optical preservation methods are equally or even more effective.

Fig. 11: Methods for securing shoe and tire tread impressions

If a shoe impression is cast in plaster, it must subsequently be digitized so that it can be further processed in the forensic workflow (e.g., entered into a case management system, added to a shoe trace collection, or prepared for a shoe comparison analysis). In most forensic laboratories, this digitization is performed using 2D photography with methods suitable for forensic applications (Fig. 12).

The Institute of Forensic Science in Bremen uses the *TrasoScan*, a versatile all-in-one 2D scanning system from the Czech company Laboratory Imaging s.r.o., for forensic digital documentation. The system is designed for high-resolution scanning (1000 PPI) of evidence (particularly shoe, tire, and glove traces, as well as shoes and fingerprints) and features versatile multispectral lighting that can be motorized, along with an integrated vacuum table for photographing thin electrostatic films (DLK). Further processing is performed using the accompanying forensic software, LIM Lucia Forensic.

Fig. 12: Photograph of a plaster cast taken with the LIM TrasoScan

Photographing track impressions is a time-consuming intermediate step and, moreover, only two-dimensional. During the molding process, the track can be destroyed, for example, by incorrect filling of the molding

compound. Furthermore, the original track is destroyed after molding, and further photography or molding is not possible.

A digital 3D image of the shoe impression taken directly at the crime scene would, in principle, be the best solution. Many products are already available on the global market from other fields that enable 3D imaging without the need for additional equipment.

For example, at the German Symposium for Tool and Shoe Marks in Vienna, Austria, in 2022, Düsseldorf expert Maikel Stiefel presented a specially developed digital 3D smartphone photogrammetry system that generated a 3D model of a shoe impression from a large number of individual photographs [2].

Fig. 13: Principle of Stiefel's Photogrammetry System KT-AR App

The system creates a virtual dome over the shoe impression and divides this dome into different sections. The user must then move the smartphone over all the sections, and a photo is automatically taken as the smartphone passes over each section. The user is shown which sections still need to be scanned. Finally, as is standard with these programs, a 3D image is reconstructed from all the individual images.

The industry has also been using 3D recording methods for years to generate 3D data from physical objects for use in technical production. There are now many mobile devices in the industry that generate 3D models using techniques such as strip light projection. As part of a study conducted at the Forensic Institute of the Bremen State Criminal Police Office, several 3D scanning devices were tested and compared alongside the Bremen plaster project [6].

The following scanning devices were tested by the Bremen Forensic Institute:

- Zeiss - T-Scan Hawk, Germany [5]
- Faro - FaroArm Quantum Max, USA [4]
- GOM - ATOS Triple Scan, Germany (now Zeiss, Germany)
- Fraunhofer Institute – Kolibri, Germany [3]
- Düsseldorf Police, Germany – Boot-Smartphone Photogrammetry [2]

Digital tests were conducted with the following two devices, but no models were generated.

- Faro - Leap ST, USA
- Faro - Freestyle 2, USA

Fig. 14: 3D scanning devices

Using the devices mentioned above, 3D measurements were taken of a plaster cast. With the *T-SCAN hawk* measuring device from *Zeiss*, two measurements were taken: a quick scan using coarse scan settings and a slow scan using fine scan settings. Two measurements were also performed using the *Fraunhofer 3DF / Kolibri* measuring device. A single image taken vertically from above, as well as five composite measurements taken from different angles.

Some 3D scanning systems require reference objects (targets, scanning markers) that must be placed around the object to be scanned (e.g., impression tray, cast). These serve as fixed reference points for the 3D scanning system. The scanner detects them automatically and uses them to track its own position and movement in space (particularly important for handheld scanners), to precisely align multiple scan passes with one another, and to increase accuracy, especially for large, symmetrical, or feature-poor objects. Without a sufficient number of visible markers, the scanner often loses tracking, and the software cannot reliably assemble the data.

Fig. 15: Orientation markers are necessary for some 3D measurements

Just as with plaster casts, preparatory steps are therefore also part of the workflow for 3D measurements.

Below, some of the measurement results are presented in their entirety; detailed images of all scans will follow later. The same features have been marked with arrows as in the plaster casts.

Clear differences between the scan results can be seen in Figures 16–18. At first view, some results appeared usable and seemed very well-suited for model identification. Whether the details were also well-represented is illustrated in the following comparison (see Table 2) of the two outlined areas (red and blue). A comparison of the detailed images revealed which 3D scanning methods were suitable for a comparative study beyond model identification

Fig. 16: 3D measurement using T-SCAN hawk with basic scan settings

Fig. 17: 3D measurement using Fraunhofer 3DF / Kolibri, 5 scans

Fig. 18: 3D Measurement using the KT-AR App by the Police Department Düsseldorf

Tab. 2: Comparison Details: Forefoot

Original Shoe Sole ToolScan

pico-crema soft blue 20°C

pico-crema soft blue -10°C

Stewalin 20°C

T-SCAN hawk, basic scan

T-SCAN hawk, advanced scan

GOM ATOS Triple Scan

3DF / Kolibri, 1 Scan

3DF / Kolibri, 5 Scans

FARO Quantum Max Scanarm

KT-AR-App, without contrast enhancement

[6]

Table 2 shows that both dental plaster and Stewalin provided very good reproduction accuracy. Even the engraved surfaces were clearly reproduced, albeit with some bubbling in the outermost areas. The individualizing features were also reproduced very clearly and could be traced down to the finest cuts and notches. A disadvantage of the Stewalin cast, however, was that it contained no coloring and, due to its white

color, reproduced the details somewhat less clearly under the microscope. This can, however, be remedied by adding a small amount of coloring.

With the 3D measuring devices, on the other hand, the details were recognizable, but depending on the level of detail, they lost some—and in some cases significant—contour accuracy due to the interconnection of the measurement points. The 3D surfaces appeared rounded and blurred the closer one looking at the details.

The image captured with the *GOM ATOS Triple Scan* 3D measuring device performed best. This device is designed only for a fixed location, making it only partially portable, very expensive, and requiring a long measurement time from many different angles to produce a clean measurement without major gaps. Even the slightest vibrations can have a significant impact on the measurement result.

The results from the mobile and practical Zeiss T-Scan Hawk were unusable for concrete forensic analysis. Here, there was a lack of detail sharpness. It is possible that future models may achieve better results.

In contrast, the 3D scans with the *Fraunhofer 3DF / Kolibri* revealed a certain amount of background noise, particularly in smooth areas, which was considered problematic for analysis aimed at definitive identification or exclusion.

The measurement using the *KT-AR app* from the Düsseldorf Police offered a good compromise between detail accuracy and image noise. The device is portable, easy to use, and scans can be taken very quickly via smartphone. Additionally, the acquisition costs are low, although the app is not yet freely available.

The two systems from *Faro*, which were not shown here, ranked between the *Zeiss T-Scan Hawk* and the *Kolibri* system in terms of image quality.

The second defined comparison area in **Table 3** presented an even greater challenge for the 3D measurement devices as well as for plaster and Stewalin: the finely structured labeling area at the shoe's joint.

The two casting methods using dental hard plaster at an outside temperature of -10°C and Stewalin also exhibited imaging weaknesses. The 3D scanning methods showed similar results regarding the details in Table 2.

The two finely meshed 3D measurements using the *FARO Quantum Max* and the *KT-AR app in the KT-Scan-Cube* performed best. Only in the case of the very small text in the upper left area did the surface rounding caused by the meshing prevail and reduce imaging accuracy more significantly. The coarsely meshed 3D measurement from *T-SCAN hawk*, on the other hand, was completely unusable, and not even the manufacturer's name was identifiable. Only the shoe size could still be roughly recognized.

The other measuring devices again clearly showed significant noise in the area of the text field, which was supposed to be rendered smoothly.

The *GOM ATOS Triple Scan* 3D measuring device, despite its good measurement results, was also rather unsuitable as a replacement or even a supplement to plaster impressions; however, it demonstrated how far 3D measurement technology has advanced and what possibilities it may offer in the future once mobile devices with this level of accuracy and resolution become available.

Tab. 3: Comparison Details: Wrist area with lettering

Original Shoe Sole ToolScan

pico-crema soft blau 20°C

pico-crema soft blau -10°C

Stewalin 20°C

T-SCAN hawk, grob

T-Scan hawk, fein

GOM ATOS Triple Scan

3DF / Kolibri, 1 Scan

3DF / Kolibri, 5 Scans

FARO Quantum Max Scanarm

KT-ScanCube, without contrast enhancement

[6]

These results demonstrate that plaster impressions continue to produce the best results. However, mobile 3D scans—taken prior to casting and providing sufficient detail—can be used as an additional safeguard and backup in case problems arise during the impression-taking process or the original is damaged.

Problems with current 3D imaging methods

When comparing 3D scanning methods with the currently standard recording methods using physical impression materials or trace photography, it quickly becomes clear that digital methods do not yet match the level of detail found in, for example, a plaster cast.

A 3D method measures the distances to a region of a surface, calculates coordinates from these measurements, and thereby generates a large number of points in a virtual space (commonly referred to as a point cloud). Depending on the measurement method, the capture process is called *triangulation* (camera/photogrammetry) or *run-time measurement* (laser/LiDAR). In standard procedures, measurements are taken from multiple angles, each generating a partial point cloud. The software then links the different partial point clouds together at recognized connection points. The raw data resulting from this process is often imperfect, which is why there are several data processing methods.

Fig. 19: Converting a point cloud into a mesh

It is impossible to completely avoid erroneous points. This is referred to as “noise.” This image noise can be removed, to a certain degree, by the software. Unfortunately, this process often results in the loss of some valid points as well. This process is usually followed by a densification of the point cloud (also known as smoothing), in which multiple points that are close together are combined into a single point with the highest possible accuracy. Some essential points can also be deleted during this process. Finally, “meshing” takes place, in which a point cloud is converted into a closed surface (e.g., through small polygonal surfaces). The better the resolution of a 3D scanner, the finer the point cloud and the smaller the polygons.

Fig. 20: Polygon meshes of different surfaces [AI generated]

For a shoe impression to be scanned, this means: The lower the resolution, the poorer the quality of a surface (such as a shoe impression) that can be reconstructed using a 3D process. The left image in Figure 20 simulates a sphere captured at low resolution. The polygon mesh is coarse and cannot reconstruct the rounded surface.

At a higher resolution, the mesh grid—as seen in the middle object in Fig. 20—is much finer, and the 3D process can make the sphere appear much rounder, even though, in detail, it is still actually composed of small flat surfaces. To the human eye, however, it appears nearly round.

The image on the right in Figure 20 shows a rough fractured pattern. However, since the details of this fracture pattern cannot be accurately represented by the polygons, a simulated surface is created. If a shoe print expert were to examine this simulated surface as if it were the actual surface, they might reach an incorrect conclusion in their analysis. And this is precisely where the danger of the 3D scanning methods currently in use lies: they do not yet accurately capture the fine details!

Summary

The Bremen Plaster Project has yielded many insights into the use of modern dental plasters in forensic science. The following points are of interest for future work with plaster used to cast impression traces:

- The setting time of dental plaster is only slightly affected by ambient temperature
- For the *pico-crema soft blue* plaster, the minimum setting time until demolding is only 30–45 minutes at low temperatures
- The more liquid the plaster is mixed, the better the impression accuracy and the less bubble formation
- Adding more water hardly extends the setting time
- Using too little water significantly reduces the working time and noticeably decreases the impression quality
- Good coloration of the dental plaster ensures better photographic results and 3D measurements

All 3D imaging methods tested here are, in comparison to a plaster impression, not yet ready for forensic analysis in terms of sufficient resolution and accuracy. Fine individual characteristics cannot yet be represented with the necessary level of detail to conduct a comparative shoe print analysis.

The best method currently available is still the plastic impression of the footprint using dental plaster or sulfur powder. Developments in 3D technology are advancing rapidly and have gained significant momentum with the integration of AI technology. However, it is essential to verify whether an AI-enhanced image quality accurately corresponds to the real trace.

For example, AI-generated interpolation to improve the representation of 3D meshes would be fatal if the individual features depicted do not correspond to the actual characteristics of the trace. In this regard, 3D methods must be closely questioned in the future.

Prospects

Experienced shoe print experts know that, in practice, the impressions submitted for analysis—whether in sand or topsoil—often lack individual characteristics. Certainly, all experts would prefer the prints shown here, which were produced under laboratory conditions in the Bremen Plaster Project. Therefore, one must indeed ask whether systems such as Maik Stiefel's photogrammetry software would not already suffice for a wide variety of prints today, since often nothing more can be extracted from them anyway. Instead of a 2D image of the crime scene impression, forensic investigators could theoretically generate a 3D image directly at the scene. This then raises the next question: who will process the data for the 3D objects so that it is available for forensic evaluation by the Forensic Science Institute? Another issue is providing sufficient storage capacity for

the large volume of data. Experience shows that each image can quickly reach the gigabyte range. When storing data for simple mass crimes, which must be retained for over 10 years in Germany, this represents a significant amount of storage space. These are all questions that must be clarified in advance when introducing such systems.

Many forensic experts around the world are now looking for alternatives to traditional casting. Since many of these forensic experts now have a background in engineering, common 3D scanning methods and their applications are well known. For this reason, there are now an increasing number of articles on 3D scanning methods for shoe prints.

In one of their articles, the British researchers Larsen and Bennett describe how the Structure from Motion (SfM) photogrammetry examined in one of their studies enabled good visualization of both group characteristics and individual characteristics and, in some cases, offered better detail resolution than other 3D scanning methods [8]. In another study by the two British forensic scientists, they report on experiments with the forensic software/freeware “DigTrace” (<https://www.digtrace.co.uk>), which is no longer supported by the company. They investigated the reliability of photogrammetry in capturing the same data when applied repeatedly to a shoe impression. In another part of their study, they examined the effects of different cameras on the results. Using point cloud-to-point cloud comparisons that measured the distance between two point clouds, they assessed the variability between the models. With their results, they aimed to demonstrate how low the variability is and confirmed the accuracy and consistency of such techniques in capturing three-dimensional traces. Using this method, 3D shoe prints on many surfaces can be captured with a repeatability of 97%, with deviations between the models amounting to less than ~0.5 mm [9]. In Bremen, too, studies have been underway for some time using the *Zephyr* software to generate 3D files via photogrammetry, which could also be used for other forensic applications (e.g., fracture matching).

Turkish forensic scientists Oğuz, Babacan, Aşıcıoğlu, and Üvet conducted a study in which they applied deep learning methods (specifically the PointNet architecture) for binary classification of 3D shoe prints using two different shoe brands. They created a 3D dataset consisting of 160 pairs of shoes. This dataset included prints of worn shoes from Adidas (nearly 800 images) and Nike (almost 2,500 images). They noted that the results were quite promising and that this type of digital analysis should be pursued further [10].

In a test, the Saudi-Egyptian mechanical engineers Abdelaal and Aldahash selected five 3D scanning technologies, including laser scanning (LS), structured light scanning (SL), smartphone photogrammetry (SP), the Microsoft Kinect v2 RGB-D camera, and the iPhone’s LiDAR sensor (iLiDAR), to test the capabilities and limitations of 3D reconstruction for shoe footprints. Another target was to use additive FDM manufacturing processes to produce models using the data from the methods. They personally concluded that the 3D-printed impression replicas exhibited superior detail accuracy compared to plaster casts (POP) [11]. However, these results are questioned in the main statement here, as the casting process using the plaster in question was not performed in a forensically correct manner (e.g., prior consolidation of the impression in loose sand, careful pouring into the impression, use of a plaster capable of detailed reproduction).

Another interesting aspect of their analysis was that none of the 3D scanning methods they used reproduced the surface structure of the sand. This suggests that the surfaces were “extrapolated” and did not show the actual trace surface. Both engineers acknowledged that preparing a plaster cast (POP/Plaster of Paris) is a messy and time-consuming process, but they avoided pointing out to the reader that the preparation prior to scanning, the capture of a 3D trace using digital methods, and the post-processing of the data all require a very significant time investment before a reasonably usable result can be delivered (this time is many times longer than for a plaster cast). Furthermore, from a European forensic perspective, none of the 3D models they

generated and presented were sufficient for directly identifying a trace as belonging to a specific shoe. This example demonstrates that studies regarding 3D scanning methods must be evaluated according to forensic standards.

As in the report authored by the State Criminal Police Office of Bremen (LKA), many researchers conclude that 3D scanning methods offer promising approaches but are not yet practical for concrete comparative analysis. However, they are already viable today for determining shoe models. Further research is needed, and all experts in the fields of shoes and tires must urgently continue to monitor technical developments in scanning equipment. The forensic field of shoe prints will not be a priority for industry, but developments in the industry may also be applicable for forensic purposes, particularly for cameras. It is possible that camera systems such as the Chinese HDX TraceTech FW10 [7], designed for shoe prints, could be used in the same way for shoe and tire impressions in the future.

Fig. 21: Possible scenario for 3D scanning using a device such as the Chinese HDX TraceTech FW10 [AI generated]

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Matthias Braune: Concept design; data curation; formal analysis; funding acquisition; investigation; methodology; project management; resources; supervision; visualization; writing parts of the original draft and revising and editing the draft; validation

Lukas Stumm: data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; project management; visualization; writing parts of the original draft and revising and editing the draft; validation

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this manuscript confirm that they have no connections to or interests in organizations or institutions that have financial or non-financial interests in the topics or materials covered in this manuscript. This is an informational transfer of scientific content from experts to experts.

STATEMENT ON DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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